

MY MOTHER TONGUE IS THE TREASURE OF MY NATION

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Annotation: This article, the most sacred wealth for man is his language, the loss of language is equal to the extinction of the nation, the stages of development of the Uzbek language: the period from Turkic to modern Uzbek literary language, the status of the Uzbek language as the state language and its historical significance, the services of Alisher Navoi the sultan of the vocabulary of our great ancestors, in the history of our language, works by Zakhiriddin Mukhammad Babur on his native language while ruling in another country, about the founder of Uzbek novels Abdulla Kodiri and his novel "Utgan kunlar", Ogahi's life and career, Cholpon's beautiful descriptions of literature, Abdulla Aripov, Erkin Vahidov, The contribution of Utkir Khoshimov to the history of Uzbek literature, in general, the great spiritual heritage left to us by our ancestors, their preservation and future hunting options are also expressed that we are responsible for the delivery to the lodge

Keywords: Language, family of turkic languages, history of Uzbek language, october 21, 1989, Alisher Navoi, Zakhiriddin Mukhammad Babur, Ogahi, Cholpon, Abdulla Kodiri, modern Uzbek literary language

Аннотация: В этой статье самым священным богатством для человека является его язык, потеря языка приравнивается к исчезновению нации, этапы развития узбекского языка: период от тюркского до современного узбекского литературного языка, Статус узбекского языка как государственного и его историческое значение, заслуги Алишера Навои, султана лексики наших великих предков, в истории нашего языка, значение его сочинений Его произведения, об основателе узбекских романов Абудулле Кодири и его романе "Утган кунлар", о жизни и творчестве Огахи, прекрасных литературных описаниях чолпона, Абдулле Арипове, Еркине Вахидове, Вклад Уткире Хошимова в историю узбекской литературы, в целом великое духовное наследие, оставленное нам нашими предками, их сохранение и будущее Также высказывают мнения, что мы несём ответственность за предоставления будущего поколения

Ключевая слова: Язык, семья тюркских языков, история узбекского языка, 21 октября 1989 г., Алишер Навои, Захириддин Мухаммад Бабур, Огахи, Чолпон, Абдулла Кодири, современный узбекский литературный язык

“Every nation is a mirror of life and language. To lose the national language is to lose the spirit of the nation”.

Abdulla Avloni

“There are more than 7,000 languages in the world. Language is the heart of a nation, its past, present and future. In this sense, the mother tongue of each nation contains its priceless treasure, thousands of words. These words have been created, polished and preserved by the people for centuries”. [1] Indeed, man is the most advanced being on the entire planet. There is only one major difference between man and other created beings. That’s the decent thing to do, and it should end there. Everyone who comes into the world has their own language. It is through this language that he is able to find his rightful place in human society.

Language is as sacred and sacred to everyone as its mother. Because the beginning of human life depends on the presence in the community, in society, of its own sweet, polite means of communication.

When we come into the world, when we recognize our memory, we begin to say mother and father in a language that combines the strange sounds that people around us are asking us to say something to. How wonderful and exciting it is to witness this process!

The role of language in the human world is incomparable. With the help of one’s mother tongue, one begins to understand new concepts and relationships. That is, as a person grows older, the ability to think and communicate with people gradually develops over the years. Language serves not only for communication or other purposes, but also to express the history of a person’s identity. It is said that before Tsarist Russia invaded ancient Turkestan, one of the Russian generals said, “If we want to occupy or destroy this nation, this country, we do not have to use force against them. Let’s take away their language, their customs, they will be wiped out,” he said. At a glance, it is clear that there is a great truth in this statement. Suppose they completely destroy the language of one nation and force it to speak the language of another nation and to follow the values of another nation? That’s right- this is not about nationalism. This is tantamount to saying that they have no purpose in life.

With the emergence of human language, he begins to say the most sacred concepts of “mother” and “father”, and grows up in the hands of those who are called by this name. begins to interact with people in the community, gaining the affection of people with polite language. In general, a person becomes a worthy member of society through his or her mother tongue.

There are so many language families in the world and so many languages that make up the link. If one of these language families is the Turkic language family, there is a beautiful language that is part of it. This is definitely Uzbek. The origin of Turkic languages goes back to ancient times. “Uzbek (Uzbek or Turkish Uzbek) is a language of the Altaic language family of Turkic languages. This language is the state language in accordance with the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. As with all languages, the history of the Uzbek literary language goes back a long way:

1. The period from BC to the 10th century. The language of this period was called ancient Turkic in science. Ancient artifacts from this period are the Orkhon-Enasay monuments. These monuments were created in the same language;
2. It is called the Old Turkic language of the XI-XIV centuries. During this period, the greatest and most important masterpieces of world literature and history, Mahmud Kashgari’s “Devonu-lug’atit-turk” (“Devon of Turkic languages”), Yusuf Khas Hajib’s “Qudadg’u bilig” (“Knowledge leading to happiness”).), Ahmad Yugnaki’s “Hibatul haqoyiq” (“The Gift of Truths”), Khorezmi’s “Love Letter”, Rabguzi’s “Rabguzi’s Story”, Gulkhani, Muqumi, Furkat, Zavqi and many other works written in the same Turkic language. missed;
3. The language used from the second half of the XIX century to the present is called “Modern Uzbek literary language”. “Works created since its publication in the Turkestan Regional Newspaper, which began in 1870, are examples of modern Uzbek literary language”. [2]

The origin of the Uzbek language mentioned above has a rich history. At the end of the twentieth century, however, there was an event that deserved to be written in capital letters on these historical pieces. That is, on October 21, 1989, Uzbek was given the status of the state language. “Although the former Soviet Constitution states that all peoples, nations, and languages in the USSR have equal rights, in practice Russian was the state language. All paperwork, mail, telegraphs, meetings at various levels, congresses, symposiums were conducted in Russian. This led to a restriction on the use of languages other than Russian, which led to justified protests. Since 1988, Uzbek intellectuals have raised the issue of restoring the rights of our language and making it the state language with a series of articles”. [3] As a result of such efforts, our language was recognized as the "State language" at the XI session of the Supreme Soviet of Uzbekistan on October 21, 1989.

When it comes to the Uzbek language, we should be proud of our native language. Because so many world-renowned adults have written and spoken in

this language. Whenever we come across a poem or a ghazal in our life, we immediately think of Alisher Navoi, the sultan of words. This is natural, of course. The reason is that at a time when no one recognizes the Turkish language and has a bad opinion of the works written in this language, Navoi completed the “Khamasa” of five epics in the same Turkic language. After this incident, the opinion of the cold-minded people about the Turkish language turned upside down. It is known from history that the beauty of the work, written in Turkish, fascinated the people of that time. The preface to the work states: “1485. “Hamsa” is finished writing. It took a total of two years to write it. Navoi points out that the great work was written in two years, and that he could write it in six months if other things did not interfere, in fact, the time it would take to write these five epics would not exceed six months.

In the midst of all this work,
Two years after five years,
Don't smoke this letter,
When you get to the end of your mouth,
If the accountant is in a hurry,
If the account of the said time turns,
It only takes six months to recover”. [4]

Alisher Navoi is not only the first person to write an epic in Turkish, but he is also credited with writing a number of works expressing the beauty of the language. For example, in his book Muhikamat ul-lug'atayn (Discussion of Two Languages), he was able to prove with convincing examples that Uzbek is no less than other languages.

Our ancestor Zahiruddin Muhammad Babur, who founded a great dynasty in India, was also one of the famous kings and poets of his time. His works are also among the great masterpieces of Uzbek literature. His pamphlet Mufassal (On Aruz) on the weight of aruz contains important information about rhyme in Turkish. This work is second only to Alisher Navoi's Mezon ul-Afzon.

We know that translating great works is not something that everyone can do. As soon as we hear the person of Muhammad Reza Ogahi, we think of one of the most advanced people of his time, who could do such a thing. Although Ogahi himself was a simple murab and was bedridden by fate, he managed to write works that have a worthy place in world literature and in the history of our country. In addition, as mentioned above, Kaykovus's “Nightmare”, Nizami Ganjavi's “Haft Paykar”, Saadi Sherozi's “Gulistan”, Badriddin Hilali's “Shah and Gado”, Abdurahman Jami's “Yusuf and Zulayho” and a number of other writers.

managed to translate into Uzbek. Agahi's main poetic legacy is written in Uzbek, all in the Taviz ul-Oshiqin divan.

When we read a novel in our daily lives, we immediately think of Abdullah Qadiri, the founder of Uzbek novels. It may sound like a simple statement, but it is a very difficult task to write a great work in the national language and enrich the literature of a nation, which serves to elevate the literature of a nation. The author's first novel in Uzbek, "Past Laughs", tells the story in perfect language, as well as the rules of etiquette of the Uzbek nation, respect for parents, zeal for the people, our people in our time. the hardships they face are beautifully described. Cholpon, the son of Abdulhamid Suleyman, is one of the great ancestors who took a worthy place in the history of Uzbek literature in the early twentieth century with his prolific work. Like his contemporaries, he devoted his life to the life of the nation, its enlightenment and spirituality. Cholpon also wrote beautiful works in Uzbek. Through the Jadid movement, he propagated enlightenment in such a way that he imagined Uzbek literature as the soul of the nation. He said of literature: "Yes, as much as we need water and air for our constantly moving body, we need as much literature for our soul, which is polluted with all sorts of filth in the way of life. If literature lives, the nation will live. We need it because it is pure water of enlightenment, bu a spring water that cleanses our eyes full of dust and dirt". [5]

Abdulla Aripov, Erkin Vahidov, Utkir Hoshimov and many other true children of the Uzbek people also contributed to the creation of the most beautiful works of the XX - XXI centuries, the recognition of the Uzbek language and Uzbek literature in the world. , will not be exaggerated.

Our ancestors, whose names are listed above and briefly describe their creations, are just a drop in the ocean. The history of the Uzbek people, language and values is so rich that it is impossible to describe them. The more good words we say in their name, the less we honor them, for the great legacy our ancestors left us.

We must remember with every breath that there is only one responsibility for the people of today. This task is to deliver the immense wealth left to us in a condition worthy of the next generation. With this in mind, at a time of rapid development, the attention to our language is growing in our country. Especially in the education system, students are taught the rich history of our language, the beautiful masterpieces of our national literature through innovative methods in the native language and literature classes, using modern technical means. By supporting talented young people, they are creating ample opportunities for the future development of Navoi, Babur, Qodiriy, Gafur Gulom. In addition, a

number of laws and regulations have been developed and amended to further enhance the prestige and use of the state language. All this will help our native language not to lose its riches, but to become stronger and more numerous.

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